

A Thin Flexible Optical Tactile Sensor Array

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Abstract. We present a flexible optical skin-like sensor array prototype, which can successfully estimate local XYZ forces and displacements with an average precision of 70 mN and 196 μm . The flexible nature of the sensor promises a non-camera-based optical tactile sensor that can instrument curved surfaces.

Keywords: Tactile · Sensor · Flexible · Array · Force · Displacement.

1 Introduction

Human skin contains dense arrays of mechanoreceptors that provide essential tactile information and enable humans to manipulate objects with incredible dexterity. Robotic grippers and prosthetic hands struggle to achieve similar dexterity in object manipulation, in part due to a lack of tactile sensation [2]. Considerable research has been dedicated to developing large-area sensory electronic skins to emulate the perceptive functions of human skin [3, 6]. However, many existing electronic skins primarily focus on pressure sensing, lacking the rich tactile information provided by mechanoreceptors, which includes the sensation of shear deformation [1].

Previously, we presented our photodiode-based optical LiVec finger tactile sensor. This sensor simultaneously measures 3D forces and displacements at ten different locations on its skin, in a compact form factor [5]. This design has an excellent frequency response at the cost of reduced spatial resolution. However, in this embodiment of the concept, as a robotic fingertip with soft outer skin, the base of the overall sensor was still rigid and planar. Here, we present a flexible skin-like array as a new member of this sensing family. This is a proof-of-concept design to investigate the ability to create a flexible optical skin-like tactile sensor which can conform to a range of surface shapes.

2 Design and Manufacture

We designed an array containing 16 sensing units arranged in a 4×4 grid. The sensing principle of each sensing unit is the same as the original LiVec sensor design [4] (Fig. 1), but the size of the sensing units has been reduced by 30%. Each sensing unit can estimate 3D point forces and displacements. The assembled sensor has dimensions of 30 mm \times 30 mm \times 7.2 mm. Each sensing unit has a 6 mm external diameter and an individual sensing range of ± 1 mm in XY and -2 mm in Z, with a 7 mm pitch between units (Fig. 1). This flexible design is more compact, containing 60% more sensing units, with a 14% decrease in centre-to-centre sensing unit density in a uniform layout, whilst

Fig. 1. The design of the flexible prototype. a) Fabricated prototype. b) Illustration of prototype layout, showing dimensions. Sensing unit 8 is highlighted and data is shown in Fig.2. c) Cross-section of a local sensing unit.

also achieving a 40% reduction in depth compared to our previous LiVec finger design [5].

The sensing electronics are assembled on a flexible, two-sided, 6-layer PCB, with the top layer only containing the light angle sensors (ADPD2140, Analog Devices) and LEDs. The skin is moulded from a two-part platinum cure silicone (Mold Star 20T) and comprises two pieces: the top skin containing the sensing structure and the base skin to hold the PCB. The sensor is assembled using seven screws around the edge of the sensor. This design means the whole sensor is flexible and can be affixed to cylindrical surfaces in this embodiment (Fig. 1).

3 Force and Displacement Calibration Procedure

Each sensing unit is calibrated using the platform described in [5, 4]. During the calibration, each individual sensing unit is individually compressed against an acrylic outcrop and moved laterally in various patterns to explore 3D space at multiple compressions (i.e., Z displacements). The data from the sensing unit, the forces applied on the sensing unit, and the sensing unit's deformations are recorded during the calibration (see [4, 5] for details). Using the data acquired during the calibration process, six separate multivariate polynomial regression models are trained for each sensing unit, using the biased (at the start of the experiment) light angle sensor photocurrent signals and the intensity (sum of four photocurrent signals) as the inputs, and the reference force or pillar tip displacement as the regression targets. This results in three separate 3rd-order models for estimating orthogonal X, Y, and Z forces and three separate 4th-order models for estimating orthogonal X, Y, and Z displacements.

4 Preliminary Results and Conclusions

The LiVec skin can successfully sense XYZ forces and displacements from each sensing unit. The average force estimate error across all sensing units is 25 ± 63 mN, -36 ± 64 mN, and 9 ± 83 mN for the X, Y, and Z forces, respectively (Fig.2). The average displacement estimate error across all sensing units is 20 ± 238 μ m, 27 ± 243 μ m, and 91 ± 61 μ m in

X, Y, and Z, respectively (Fig.2). The new prototype design uses a flexible PCB, making the overall sensor flexible and conformable to curved surfaces. The small thickness and flexibility of the overall sensor aim to mimic human skin, meaning it can be implemented as a large-area tactile skin.

Fig. 2. a) Estimated against truth, XYZ forces of sensing unit 8, which is highlighted in Fig.1. b) Average bias and precision of all the sensing units for force and displacement.

Our future work will focus on calibrating global forces and torques, ensuring that the force and displacement calibration equations remain valid when the sensor's curvature is varied, adapting the outer skin shape to more closely mimic fingerprint patterns, and integrating the design with a robotic hand to demonstrate its utility.

Acknowledgments. This work was funded by the Innovation in Haptics call of The IEEE Technical Committee on Haptics and supported by Science Foundation Ireland President of Ireland Future Research Leaders Award (17/FRL/4832).

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

References

1. Duan, Y., He, S., Wu, J., Su, B., Wang, Y.: Recent Progress in Flexible Pressure Sensor Arrays. *Nanomaterials* **12**(14), 2495 (Jan 2022). <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano12142495>
2. Kappasov, Z., Corrales, J.A., Perdereau, V.: Tactile sensing in dexterous robot hands — Review. *Robotics and Autonomous Systems* **74**, 195–220 (Dec 2015). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.robot.2015.07.015>
3. Lee, Y., Park, J., Choe, A., Cho, S., Kim, J., Ko, H.: Mimicking Human and Biological Skins for Multifunctional Skin Electronics. *Advanced Functional Materials* **30**(20), 1904523 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.201904523>
4. Leslie, O., Córdova Bulens, D., Martinez Ulloa, P., Redmond, S.J.: A Tactile Sensing Concept for 3-D Displacement and 3-D Force Measurement Using Light Angle and Intensity Sensing. *IEEE Sensors Journal* **23**(18), 21172–21188 (Sep 2023). <https://doi.org/10.1109/JSEN.2023.3293967>
5. Leslie, O., Córdova Bulens, D., Redmond, S.J.: Design, Fabrication, and Characterization of a Novel Optical Six-Axis Distributed Force and Displacement Tactile Sensor for Dexterous Robotic Manipulation. *Sensors* **23**(24), 9640 (Jan 2023). <https://doi.org/10.3390/s23249640>
6. Wang, C., Liu, C., Shang, F., Niu, S., Ke, L., Zhang, N., Ma, B., Li, R., Sun, X., Zhang, S.: Tactile sensing technology in bionic skin: A review. *Biosensors and Bioelectronics* **220**, 114882 (Jan 2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2022.114882>